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Data Review

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Abstract

The dataset is the first-wave release of the international 'Values in Crisis' (VIC) survey, designed to measure citizens' values, attitudes, and crisis experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic. The project was initiated by an international academic team and coordinated with the Austrian Social Science Data Archive. The questionnaire covers several thematic blocks. It includes standard socio-demographics (gender, year of birth, marital status, children, education, etc.), followed by detailed items on COVID-19 experiences and perceptions.

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Review of the Values in Crisis study

by Stas Gorelik

The dataset is the first-wave release of the international ‘Values in Crisis’ (VIC) survey, designed to measure citizens’ values, attitudes, and crisis experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic. The project was initiated by an international academic team and coordinated with the Austrian Social Science Data Archive, with national teams fielding comparable surveys—online and through quota sampling—across 17 countries, including Georgia, Russia, and Kazakhstan in the post-Soviet region.¹

The questionnaire covers several thematic blocks. It includes standard socio-demographics (gender, year of birth, marital status, children, education, etc.), followed by detailed items on COVID-19 experiences and perceptions. These include exposure to COVID-related health risks (self and close others), economic disruption (job loss, reduced work, home office, aid receipt), perceived health and economic threats, evaluations of government performance and social behavior, perceived solidarity versus hostility, outlook for national recovery, mental well-being indicators, and belief in social media claims that the pandemic was a hoax.

Importantly, the timing of fieldwork varies across the countries included in the dataset. In most cases, surveys were conducted in spring 2020, while in the remaining countries fieldwork took place roughly six months later. Given the rapidly evolving pandemic context, this temporal variation complicates the interpretation of cross-country differences.

The survey further measures value orientations using widely used instruments, including a short version of Schwartz’s Portrait Value Questionnaire items commonly used in the European Values Study and World Value Survey (e.g., national pride, respect for authority, religion). In addition, the data includes a number of personality measures and a set of social and political orientation questions intended to capture broader evaluative and normative attitudes during the pandemic.

Data access: <https://data.aussda.at/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.11587/LIHK1L>.

¹ Fieldwork dates: Georgia: May 28 - June 9, 2020 (n = 1059); Kazakhstan: May 5 - June 1, 2020 (n = 1035); Russia: June 10-16, 2020 (n = 1527).